

A Critical Review of Problems Facing Mathematics Teachers in Basic Schools in Nigeria

Abstract:

Secondary data collected from print and online publication was employed to discuss the problems facing mathematics teachers in the Nigerian Basic schools. The paper argued that mathematics is a very important subject in the Basic schools that needs proper administrations and curriculum implementations in order to realize its objectives. The paper concluded that teaching of large classes, inadequate mathematics laboratory, shortage of instructional materials, poor motivation, ineffective capacity building programme, poor supervision and negative attitude of students towards learning of mathematics are some of the major problems mathematics teachers are facing in the realization of Nigerian Basic schools mathematics goals. The paper hereby recommended that the government should increase the funding of Basic school education in Nigeria. This will help to employ more teachers and provide more infrastructure facilities like mathematics laboratories, mathematics instructional materials and improve the supervision of mathematics teachers and capacity building programme.

Keywords:

Basic Schools, Mathematics Teachers, Mathematics goals.

Information about the authors

Sunday A. O.

*Department of Science and Environmental Education, Faculty of
Education, University of Abuja, Nigeria*

Dr. Onoge Honmane

*Department of Science Education, Federal University Wukari, Taraba
State, Nigeria*

Introduction

Mathematics programme is one of the compulsory subjects offered in the Nigerian Basic schools; and it is meant to develop the mathematical skills of the students because usefulness of mathematics is applicable to every sphere human daily living. Emmanuel, & Daniel, (2017) submitted that there is no doubt that mathematics has extensive applications in life and related fields. Professional observations showed that mathematics is a language and mathematics is a gate-way to science. Mathematics is the language upon which science, commerce, industry, internet and the entire global economic infrastructure depend. Mathematics is the only “true” universal language and it is an essential part of our personal and working life. Mathematics is not only a language and a subject, it is also critical in fostering logical, rigorous thinking, as such, its influence is immense. Everyone recognizes that it is vital to be able to read and write basic language (e.g. English) for effective communication. In mathematics, the equivalence of basic reading and writing is numeracy; as numbers are the sounds, syllables and words of the mathematics language.

Mathematics programme, one of the fundamental subjects offered in the Nigerian educational sector and in the rest of the World is one of the most affected by the problem of lack of planning. Mathematics is an essential discipline which forms the basis for all other sciences and deals with the material substance of space and time. Mathematics can be divided into pure and applied mathematics. Pure mathematics focuses on concepts which are based on the rules of mathematics, though the aim of these concepts is not necessarily for meeting the needs of the physical world alone but also deal with the determination of mathematical proofs. Applied mathematics on the other hand is that branch of Mathematics which is applied to other branches such as Chemistry, Physics, Engineering, etc., as it focuses on a problem-solving approach. It attempts to discover practical solutions to solving the everyday problems of life. In practical life, pure mathematics and applied mathematics overlap each other. The concepts of pure mathematics are also used by applied mathematics to discover practical solutions (Info-guide Nigeria, 2018 and Ogunode, 2020).

Emmanuel and Daniel (2017) noted that Mathematics is more than just the science of numbers taught by teachers in schools and either enjoyed or feared by many students; it also played a significant role in the lives of individuals, the society and the world as a whole. Mathematics is an essential discipline recognized worldwide and it needs to be augmented in education to equip student with skills necessary for achieving higher education, career aspiration, and for attaining personal fulfillment. Since mathematics encompasses all aspects of human life, it is unquestionably important in education to help students and all people from all walks of life to perform their daily tasks efficiently and become productive, well informed, functional, independent individuals and members of a society, where mathematics is the fundamental component. Mathematicians create so-called models of the world, and study them. These models apply even to the simplest mathematics. The problem usually start after the age of five or six, instead of studying addition by actually combining groups of real objects and counting them; we use an abstract mathematics contraction or model known as the positive integers i.e (the numbers 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, and so on). Once again, Mathematicians study models so as to idealize world of intangible things that we do not come across in everyday life. For example, talking of a perfect circle, this does not concern tangible worldly thing like chairs, table and so on.

Festus, (2014) opined that Mathematics is the foundation for the economic and technological development of any nation. It has been asserted that without mathematics, there cannot be any modern developed society (Ukeje, 2005). This assertion accounts for the reason why Mathematics is made a compulsory subject at the Basic and Secondary School levels in Nigeria (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2014). Thus, mathematics is expected to help in accelerating social, economic and technological progress of any society. Achieving all these progresses, in the final analyses, depend on the effective teaching and learning of mathematics in schools. The Basic school level is very important in any educational system because any default at this level would permeate to other levels of the educational system. Realization of the objectives of teaching mathematics at any level of the educational system in the society call for employment of professional Mathematics teachers in the Basic schools.

Mathematics Teacher

A professional mathematics teacher is trained individual, certified to teach mathematics programme at a level of educational system depending on the qualification requirement. A mathematics teacher is a person that has undergone training in the field of mathematics education and has been certified to teach in the school system. A mathematics teacher can be a holder of Nigerian certificate of education NCE, Bachelor of Science Education B.Sc. (Ed.), Masters of Education M.Ed. or Doctor of Philosophy PhD in Mathematics Education. Mathematics teachers are employed in educational institutions to implement the mathematics curriculum at the level of their professional training acquired.

The responsibilities of a mathematics teacher include implementation of mathematics programme, organization of mathematics instructional resources, writing of lesson plan and lesson note, taking students for excursion, assessment of students via continuous assessment and examination, preparation

of report sheet and provision of feedback to parents on students' academic progress. Mathematics teachers are found in all the Nigerian educational institutions especially in the Basic schools across the country. The job performance of the Mathematics teachers in Basic schools may be hampered if these identified challenges still face the Mathematics teachers in the course of discharging their duties.

Problems Facing Mathematics Teachers in Basic Schools in Nigeria

There are many challenges facing mathematics teachers in the Basic schools. The challenges include; teaching of large classes, nonavailability or ill-equipped mathematics lab, shortage of instructional materials, poor motivation, ineffective capacity building programme, poor supervision and negative attitude of students towards the learning of mathematics.

Teaching of large classes

Some mathematics teachers in Nigerian Basic schools are faced with the challenges of teaching large classes. A class is considered large if the number of learners is significantly more than the acceptable number as specify in the National policy on education. The Nigerian national policy on education (2014) put the teacher-student ratio for basic school at 1:30, but it has been observed from studies that some mathematics teachers teaching in Basic schools are teaching students who are considerably more in number than the stated number in the national policy. A survey study carried out by Abubakar (2015) found that teacher-student ratio for mathematics class in some Basic school in Kano State was mostly 1:100. Also, Festus (2014) discovered that one of the challenges facing teaching and learning of mathematics include teaching of large class size. Musa (2013) submitted that teachers that are teaching large classes are overstretched and are significantly of lower performance.

Inadequate Mathematics Lab

Mathematics laboratory is a special room furnished with mathematics resources for the teaching and learning of mathematics. Mathematics laboratory is designed for the implementation of mathematics programme in the schools. Proper usage of mathematics laboratory helps to simplify the teaching and learning of mathematical skills and its availability is critical for the teaching and learning of mathematics in educational institutions. It is unfortunate that some Basic schools across Nigeria do not have adequately equipped mathematics laboratory for their teachers and students; and this has affected the implementation of mathematics curriculum in such schools (Abubakar, 2015). Femi (2016) blamed the lack, inadequacy and poor equipment of mathematics laboratory in Basic schools on inadequate funding of Basic schools in Nigeria by financial stakeholders. Festus (2014) found out that most basic schools are faced with the problems of; lack of materials for organizing tests; lack of time to organize tests and do corrections for pupils; lack of infrastructure facilities, lack of preparation by the pupils for assessment; lack of knowledge about assessment techniques by some teachers; poor attitude of teachers to assessment due to poor condition of service.

Shortage of Instructional Materials

Musa (2015) conducted a study on the availability and deployment of mathematics instructional materials in Basic schools in Katsina State and discovered that many mathematics teachers are teaching without the application of instructional materials due to shortage and non-availability of it in the Basic schools. Another study carried out by Emmanuel (2013) to find the causes of shortage of mathematics instructional materials in Niger State basic schools concluded that inadequate funding, poor planning, poor improvisation skills by teachers, corruption and lack of storage facilities to preserve and maintain the instructional resources are challenges facing instructional resources for mathematics teaching. Ekwueme, Meremikwu and Kalu (2013) submitted that most of the headteachers of Basic schools sampled in their research indicated that they are faced with the problem of shortages of classroom blocks, textbooks to distribute to teachers and students, libraries, laboratories, and equipment for mathematics. No provision for mathematics laboratory, making it difficult for them to safeguard some delicate projects produced during workshops and some that were

supplied by book publishers, mathematics centre Abuja, and NERDC during workshops and seminars. Info-guide Nigeria (2018); Sunday, Obed, & Yalwa, (2018); Iproject- (undated) and Lawase Sunday & Ogunode (2021) observed that most educational institutions in Nigeria lack adequate mathematics instructional materials.

Poor Motivation

Mathematics teachers in Nigerian Basic schools are poorly motivated. Motivation plays an important role in the organization because it increases the productivity of employees and the goals can be achieved in an efficient way. Attitude to work and behavior of employees can be influenced through motivation in any organization. From situation to situation, the form or level of motivation differs with in an individual (Robbins, Judge, and Sanghi, 2005). Motivation also play an important role in teaching as it helps teachers to achieve the target goal in an efficient way. Teacher motivation is very important because it improves the skills and knowledge of teachers and it is indirectly influencing the students' achievements in learning (Mustafa, and Othman, 2010). Adelabu (2005) found in Nigeria that teachers' motivation package is very poor as teachers are mostly dissatisfied with their working environment and salary conditions. The reason behind the poor motivation of teachers is that they having low salaries as compared to other professionals, poor work environment, lack of autonomy in decision making authority, and lack of opportunity to further develop their career. A study by Adeyemi (2015) confirmed that mathematics teachers teaching in some Nigerian schools are poorly motivated.

Ineffective Capacity Building Programme

Poor capacity building programme is another problem mathematics teachers teaching at the Nigerian basic schools are facing. This submission is supported by Faith (2013) who carried out a study that investigated the challenges facing teaching and learning of mathematics programme in some selected primary schools. The result revealed that the challenges facing the teaching and learning of mathematics programme includes; poor capacity development of mathematics teachers, inadequate professional mathematics teachers, inadequate funding of mathematics programme, and inadequate mathematics instructional materials. The inability of the mathematics teachers to access constant training and retraining programmes has affected the performance and productivity of mathematics teachers. Ekwueme, Meremikwu and Kalu (2013) also discovered in their study that only 40% of all the respondents had attended workshops, 41% attended seminars while 12.5% ever attended short-term training. Also, about 13% respondents indicated that they had not attended any of the programmes. It was also observed that the public primary school mathematics teachers had more opportunity to attend those organized programmes with 65% and 75% for workshop and seminar respectively. Though for the Basic school teachers and the secondary schools teachers, less than 50% attendance was recorded for the programmes. This, therefore, means that the participation level of the mathematics teachers to those organized programmes is still low with less than 50% attendance in any of the above-listed programmes for most of the teachers.

Poor Supervision

Supervision is meant for professional development of teachers. Supervision of teachers is a key to improve the quality and capacity of the teachers. Teachers that are well supervised performed better than teachers that are not constantly been supervised. Mathematics teachers need constant supervision due to the fact that mathematics programme is technical and that required professional skills for effective teaching. It is unfortunate that majorities of mathematics teachers presently teaching in the Basic schools across the country are not being supervised effectively. This submission is attested to by Ogunode & Emmanuel, (2021) who did a study in FCT and found out that one of the problem facing teaching and learning of mathematics in primary schools is poor supervision of mathematics programme. Betiku, (2001) and Femi (2016) observed that mathematics teachers in most educational institutions in Nigeria are poorly supervised. Poor supervision of Basic schools in Nigeria are caused

by according to Ogunode (2021) poor funding, shortage of supervisors, insecurity problem, inadequate transport facilities, poor training and corruption.

Negative Attitude of Students Towards Learning of Mathematics

Another problem mathematics teachers teaching in Basic schools are facing is the negative altitude of mathematics students towards the learning of mathematics as a subject. This submission is confirmed by Ogunode & Emmanuel, (2021) that concluded that the negative attitude of students towards the study of mathematics programme at the primary schools has affected the learning of mathematics and hampered the implementation of the programme to achieve its goals. Also, Iproject.com (2018) observed that the problems associated with teaching and learning of mathematics is seen from the lukewarm attitudes of some mathematics teachers and their ineffectiveness in mathematics education. Lack of student-teacher relationship has also been seen in the environment in which teaching and learning is conducted. Teaching and learning of mathematics in secondary schools is very essential, no doubt because, it is regarded as a yardstick in the development of any nation. Shield and Kelly (1999) conducted a study that sourced information from principals on reasons for poor performance in mathematics. The principals gave the following reasons: learners' attitude towards learning mathematics in schools; ineffective support for mathematics students; poor capacity development of mathematics teachers; inadequate or shortage of instructional materials for teaching mathematics; poor coverage of the scheme of work for mathematics programme and inadequate time allocated for mathematics programme. Festus (2014) did a study and the result revealed many problems facing the implementing good assessments of pupils in mathematics at the primary school level in Nigeria. Some of them include: lack of interest by pupils; Absenteeism, lateness and truancy of pupils from school etc.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Mathematics subject is one of the compulsory subject offered in the Nigerian Basic schools designed to develop the mathematical skills of students at the Basic schools level. Mathematics is very important subject in the Basic schools that needs proper administrations in order to realize its objectives. Therefore, adequate funding of mathematics subject in the Basic schools is critical for the development of the programme as it will help to provide needed human and materials resources for smooth implementation of mathematics curriculum. Adequate funding will also help to provide adequate training and retraining programme for the mathematics teachers and to improve their allowance. Satisfactory funding of mathematics programme will aid effective administration of mathematics programme at the Basic school level. To realize the objectives of mathematics programme at the Basic school level, there is need for continuous investment into the programme.

The paper draw the following conclusion that teaching of large classes, inadequate mathematics laboratory, and shortage of instructional materials, poor motivation, ineffective capacity building programme, poor supervision and negative attitude of students towards learning of mathematics are among the major problems mathematics teachers in the Nigerian Basic schools face on daily basis. Therefore, the following are recommended:

1. Increment in the funding of Basic school education in Nigeria by the government. This will help to employ more teachers which will reduce the high teacher-student ratio in the classes.
2. The government should provide well-equipped mathematics laboratory in all the schools alongside other laboratories to safeguard mathematics equipment, concretize the teaching of mathematics, and also projects produced during workshop for further use;
3. Constant training and retraining programme should be organized for mathematics teachers.
4. More mathematics instructional materials should be provided for mathematics teachers in all Basic schools in the country.

5. Government should increase salaries and allowances of mathematics teachers to motivate them in the Basic schools.
6. The government should direct for effective supervision of mathematics teachers in all the Basic schools.
7. Students should be encourage and motivated to study mathematics subject in all the basic schools across the country.

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